

Evidence-based regulation: Article 88b Digital Omnibus

Increasing consumer awareness and consent rates through the appropriate design of agent-based consent

Authors:

Dr. Nina Gerber (Psychology)

Paul Graßl (Behavioral Science)

Prof. Dr. Timo Jakobi (Human Computer Interaction)

Prof. Dr. Max von Grafenstein, LL.M. (Regulation & Innovation)

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Executive summary

- The introduction of consent agents, as provided for in **Article 88b Digital Omnibus, is currently the only known method for enabling consumers to make informed decisions** (at least in the case of frequently recurring consent requests) and thus to obtain consent that meets the legal requirements.
- The **specific (visual) design of agent-based consent mechanisms plays a key role** in determining
 - how well or poorly they actually inform consumers,
 - how they affect consumers' trust in the service used and in the sharing of their personal data, and
 - the consent rate.
- **The study currently being circulated by Google** in the EU Commission's offices in Brussels (as yet unpublished) on the allegedly devastating economic consequences of Article 88b of the Digital Omnibus Directive on the EU Single Market **is highly misleading**, because
 - it takes Apple's introduction of App Tracking Transparency (ATT) as its starting point and, thus, an example of how agent-based consent mechanisms should not be designed;
 - it is these very practices that the level playing field established by Article 88b for all providers is intended to prevent by ensuring fair competition.
- With ATT, Apple has centralised the consent process for the processing of personal data in mobile apps for all third-party apps in such a way that consent rates have fallen sharply; while Apple obtains consent for its own data processing via more favourable mechanisms (and has since expanded its advertising business).
- In contrast, empirical comparative studies on the design for consent agents show that **agent-based consent mechanisms can increase consent rates by up to almost 20%** compared to traditional status quo cookie banners – if properly designed.
- Thanks to the transparency and decision-making efficiency enabled by Article 88b Digital Omnibus, which is applicable to all services, such services that comply with the law are now, for the first time, able to successfully distinguish themselves from other services offering a lower standard of data protection.
- Article 88b and Article 88a(4) of the Digital Omnibus Act should be clarified accordingly. Only by doing so, the EC meets, in the area of informed consent, its own "immediate objective (..) to ensure that compliance with the rules comes at a lower cost, delivers on the same objectives, and brings in itself a competitive advantage to responsible businesses."

The negative effects of current intransparent and fatiguing cookie banners on trust and the economy

Current cookie banners and similar consent mechanisms do not allow for informed decisions. Their lack of both transparency and control for users gives rise to three serious drawbacks:

1. The level of informedness is so low that there is **effectively no ‘informed’ consent** within the meaning of data protection law.¹ This leads to considerable legal uncertainty among businesses that base their data processing on consent.
2. The current design of consent leads to a **high level of mistrust among consumers** towards digital services in general. This mistrust results in reduced consent rates, and, especially in cases where consent is ‘forced’ (such as in the ‘Pay or Okay’ model), reduced service uptake.
3. Consumers cannot distinguish between privacy-friendly services and those with high privacy risks. Services with high privacy risks therefore gain **unfair competitive advantages** by achieving the same consent rates as privacy-friendly services, even though they invest significantly less in the compliance of their services.

In conclusion, this situation **undermines the trust** of consumers and compliant businesses **in the effectiveness of our rule of law**. Everyone knows that the current consent process is a farce. The state is being held responsible for it – even though a legally secure, informative and trust-building design of the consent process is possible.

Empirical evidence for increased awareness, trust and consent rates through agent-based consent

How effectively consent mechanisms inform consumers, and to what extent this influences their trust in sharing their data and the consent rate, depends on how they are designed.

How consent forms should not be designed: the example of Apple’s ATT

A negative example of this is the introduction of **Apple’s App Tracking Transparency (ATT)**. This consent mechanism is designed in such a way that it has led to a significant drop in consent rates among app providers; meanwhile, Apple uses a different consent mechanism for its own processing purposes, with a design that is far more favourable to itself, and has since significantly expanded its advertising business.

According to a scientific study, ATT leads to average ad impression price decreases of between 18% and 23%.² Assuming that the EU digital advertising market is worth approximately €80–100 billion annually, and that tracking-based advertising accounts for, at least, over 50%, ATT results in a loss of several billion euros per year in the EU.

¹ Grassl, P., Gerber, N., & Grafenstein, M. v. (2024). How Effectively Do Consent Notices Inform Users About the Risks to Their Fundamental Rights? *European Data Protection Law Review*, 10(1), 96-104. DOI: 10.21552/edpl/2024/1/14; extended version with visual designs and charts at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5012997.

² Laub, R., Miller, K., Skiera, B., The Economic Value of User Tracking for Publishers.

Google is currently circulating a study – not available to the public – within the offices of the EU legislature, in which it uses this decline in consent rates and revenue as a basis and extrapolates the figures to the EU economy as a whole. These figures are currently causing widespread alarm. However, this study is highly misleading because it is based on a consent model that Article 88b is specifically designed to prevent. If properly drafted, Article 88b does not only mitigate these effects, but turns them into positive effects.

Consent agents as a condition for informed and user-friendly consent

Given necessary clarifications, Article 88b ensures that consent mechanisms are implemented in such a way that they demonstrably better inform consumers, increase their trust in the processing of their data and increase the likelihood that they will consent to processing their data. Agent-based consent processes play a key role in this.

Consent agents handle a significant proportion of frequently recurring consent requests by informing end users of the purposes for which digital services typically wish to process their data, and thereby seeking their consent or allowing them to object. **In consent agents, users can set preferences**, which the agent then passes on to the service provider when the service is used. In doing so, the provider can inform the user about the specific level of data protection in an easily understandable manner via a so-called handover notice; the user can adjust their preferences accordingly, but is not obliged to do so. If the user makes no adjustments, the handover notice disappears automatically after a short time.

This mechanism allows users to access key information and make fundamental decisions at a time of their (!) choosing; in doing so, it prevents the informational overload and consent fatigue that result from traditional cookie banner designs. **Consent agents can have strong positive effects on informedness and consent rates**, which have been scientifically demonstrated, in particular, by the following two recent empirical studies.

Quantitative longitudinal field study proving the increase in consent rates through agent-based consent mechanisms

Study design: In this quantitative long-term field study involving around 1,000 participants within the EU (including the UK), a total of 10 different consent mechanisms were compared against one another; the testers used these mechanisms over a four-week period whilst browsing the internet on their computer. The choice of a long-term field study ensured that the real-world effects of using a consent agent could be examined by observing the testers' decision-making behaviour over an extended period, i.e. across many different websites visited. The consent mechanisms compared in this **A/B/n test** ranged from a cookie banner designed according to current best practice guidelines (status quo banner) to various versions of agent-based consent mechanisms developed over an iterative research process spanning around five years.³ Over the course of four weeks, each tester in each group visited an average of around 120 websites; in total, over 2 million data points were collected.

Study results: The study results prove significant differences between the various consent designs. In particular, they show that almost all alternative consent mechanisms have higher consent rates than the Status Quo Cookie Banner in study group A (see Annex). However, the results also show that the consent rate depends heavily on the specific visual design of

³ See for further references at Grafenstein, M. v., Kiefaber, I., Heumüller, J., Rupp, V., Graßl, P., Kolless, O., & Puzst, Z. (2024). Privacy icons as a component of effective transparency and controls under the GDPR: effective data protection by design based on art. 25 GDPR. CLSR, 52. DOI: 10.1016/j.clsr.2023.105924; Smieskol, P., Jakobi, T., & von Grafenstein, M. (2025). From consent to control by closing the feedback loop: Enabling data subjects to directly compare personalized and non-personalized content through an On/Off toggle. CLSR, 59, 1-22, November 2025.

the consent mechanism. In a positive sense, this is particularly evident in study group G, which shows **increases in the consent rate of between approximately 8% and 19%** compared to the standard cookie banner. On the negative side, the effects of the specific visual design are very visible in study group H, where end users had to actively reconfirm their default settings from the agent on the website; this was ignored by most users – evidently because they had already expressed their active decision within the agent and a second active confirmation seemed unnecessary to them in many cases – with the result that consent was not given, even though it had been given in the default settings in many instances.

We leave it to the reader to extrapolate these increases in consent rates to the wider EU economy. **The key question is whether these higher consent rates genuinely reflect improved user informedness. Prior quantitative work provides evidence that they do.**

Quantitative study on informedness (as well as competitive advantages for data protection friendly services)

Study design: The design of this quantitative study mainly focused on the level of informedness among testers by using various consent mechanisms. In this test, 349 participants visited a website – an online plant shop set up for this test – without knowing that the consent mechanisms displayed were part of the test (i.e. a so-called cover story). The consent mechanisms compared in this A/B/n test also ranged from a standard cookie banner designed in accordance with current best-practice guidelines to various versions of agent-based consent mechanisms, however, with this study being limited to five test groups. The consent rate was measured as well; this included whether the rate changed when the website indicated, during a visit by the testers of these study groups using a consent agent, that it offered an above-average level of data protection (study groups 4 and 5).

Study results: On the one hand, the study repeatedly demonstrates – as was already the case in the study referred to earlier⁴ – the low level of informedness regarding the status quo cookie banner; on the other hand, it also shows that informedness is substantially higher when it comes to alternative consent mechanisms. This higher level of awareness is particularly evident in the third test group, which used a consent agent; and even more so in

⁴ See fn. 1.

the fourth test group, which also provided information on a particularly high level of data protection on the visited online shop website.

The findings are highly relevant, supported by an adequately sized sample. This relevance is underscored by numerous qualitative studies, which explain the higher level of informedness through the following factors:⁵

1. The test subjects were shown not only the processing purposes (which were already used in the status quo cookie banner but formulated in a more comprehensible manner), but also the benefits and risks associated with the respective data processing for them.
2. The consent agent provides an additional, distinct 'touchpoint' in terms of timing and visual presentation, where test subjects could inform themselves about the significance of giving consent.
3. This effect is reinforced by specific additional information when visiting the actual website.

The most important factor for the legal policy-making process is that these studies are still relatively 'naive' visual concept studies. This means that there is plenty of scope for design improvements to further enhance the level of informedness. This applies in particular to the 'handover notice', through which consumers can be convinced to give their consent by being informed of the above-average level of data protection offered by the service they are visiting, even if they had not yet consented to a specific purpose in their consent agent. With the appropriate clarification in Article 88b, this design space can be used over the next few years to enable even more increasing levels of informedness, trust and consent rates.

⁵ See for further references fn. 3.

Necessary clarification in Article 88b: Ensuring that consumers can make truly informed decisions

To ensure this trend towards increasingly informative, trust-building consent mechanisms – and consequently higher consent rates – Article 88b must be clarified accordingly. This includes ensuring that providers of consent mechanisms (whether they are providers of consent agents or cookie banners, which are required to integrate communication with consent agents) ensure the following factors:

1. both must enable genuinely informed decisions; to this end, clear reference must be made to Article 25 of the GDPR, which already requires proof of the effective implementation of informed consent and other decisions, as well as compliance with the most effective implementation in each case (the so-called state of the art),⁶
2. cookie banners must provide end users for a link to implement their consent agent if they want to; providers of browsers and operating systems must integrate consent agents in their systems in the most usable way (maximum two clicks); digital services must comply with the settings provided by the consent agents and may only display a cookie banner again if they need to notify users of improvements or reductions in the specific level of data protection of their service;
3. whilst always ensuring a fair balance of interests with the needs of data processing entities, particularly SMEs; to this end, accreditation is mandatory, ideally in accordance with Articles 10 et seq. of the DGA, to avoid duplicate accreditation structures.

It goes without saying that browser providers who are designated as gatekeepers under the Data Market Act must not themselves offer such (agent-based) consent mechanisms. This would be tantamount to putting the fox in charge of the henhouse, further increasing the already dominant market power of these providers.

If these requirements are implemented accordingly in Article 88b, this would not only fulfil the EU legal policy commitment “that compliance with the rules comes at a lower cost, delivers on the same objectives, and brings in itself a competitive advantage to responsible businesses.”⁷ Article 88b would also finally boost consumers’ confidence in the processing of their data, thereby enhancing the economic and social value of data – and strengthening everyone’s confidence in the effectiveness of the rule of European data law.

⁶ See EDPB Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default, which sets the proof for effectiveness into the center of implementing the GDPR provisions, such as informed consent as well as objections and so on, pp. 6 et seq.

⁷ See at <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-omnibus-regulation-proposal>.

Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG): The [Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society](#) (HIIG) was founded in 2011 to research the development of the internet from a societal perspective and better understand the digitalisation of all spheres of life. As the first institute in Germany with a focus on internet and society, HIIG has established an understanding that centres on the deep interconnectedness of digital innovations and societal processes. The development of technology reflects norms, values and networks of interests, and conversely, technologies, once established, influence social values.

Einstein Center Digital Future (ECDF): The [Einstein Center Digital Future](#) (ECDF) is the center for digitalization research in Berlin. It is based on a large-scale public-private partnership (PPP) model between more than 30 companies, organizations, all four Berlin universities, the Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin and more than ten other of Berlin's research institutions. With 38.5 million euros in funding, ECDF aims to connect Berlin's actors in the field of digitalization, test new forms of cooperation, foster innovative and interdisciplinary research, and to attract excellent junior scholars from around the world.

Universität der Künste Berlin: The Berlin University of the Arts (UdK Berlin) is one of the largest and most diverse art universities in Europe, where artistic teaching and practice intersect with academic discourse to shape its distinctive profile. With a history spanning more than 300 years, it is deeply rooted in the city of Berlin and, with more than 700 events each year, serves as a significant cultural driving force. UdK Berlin unites a broad spectrum of study programmes in Fine Arts, Design, Music, Performing Arts, and the academic disciplines related to these fields.

Consenter research demonstrator (Law & Innovation Technology): Several of the aforementioned studies have been conducted based on the research demonstrator [Consenter](#), developed by the academic spin-off Law & Innovation Technology GmbH. Consenter is the result of an interdisciplinary research process developed in collaboration with numerous research institutions and data protection authorities, including HIIG, ECDF and UdK. The development of the research demonstrator was funded by the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space. In 2025, the Federal Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information (BfDI) recognised Consenter as the world's first data protection-compliant consent management service (see [BfDI register](#)). This makes Consenter the first officially recognised solution to the cookie banner problem.

ATHENE: The [ATHENE National Research Center for Applied Cybersecurity](#) is the largest research center for applied cybersecurity and privacy protection in Europe. ATHENE is a joint research center of the Technical University of Darmstadt, Darmstadt University of Applied Sciences, and the Fraunhofer Institute for Secure Information Technology SIT and Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research IGD. ATHENE is funded by the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR) and the Hessian Ministry of Science and the Arts (HMWK).

Ohm-UX Competence Center, Technical University of Applied Sciences Nürnberg: The Ohm-UX, founded in 2006 is an interdisciplinary research center combining expertise from human-computer interaction, design, computer science, and economics. It conducts both industry-funded research and publicly funded third-party projects, focusing on the empirical evaluation and design of the wide variety of human-centered digital systems. Using methods from usability engineering, behavioral science, and experimental research, Ohm-UX investigates how to design for optimizing interactive experiences.

Annex – visual designs of consent mechanisms used in the quantitative longitudinal field study

Maol

Study Group G

Feedback

My Pre-Settings

Configure your pre-settings once beforehand - we will then hand them over automatically whenever you visit a website.

With your consent you enable the processing of your data for the following purposes:

Improve the website

Benefits

- Improved usability in the future

Risks

- Statistical insight into how you use the website
- Data transfer outside the EU

Do you agree?

MY PLANTSHOP

SO MANY AMAZING PLANTS

- Improve the website
Benefit Risk Ratio 3:2
- Enable additional website features
Benefit Risk Ratio 6:3
- Customise the website for you
Benefit Risk Ratio 10:12
- Personalised advertisement
Benefit Risk Ratio 10:12

Save for this site only
save locally

Save for further sites
save in Consentor Cloud

Learn more at [consentor](#)

MY PLANTSHOP

SO MANY AMAZING PLANTS

Your consent will be sent to this website in 20 seconds

Pause and see more

Maol

Study Group H

Feedback

My Pre-Settings

Configure your pre-settings once beforehand - we will then hand them over automatically whenever you visit a website.

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Improve the website

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Risks

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Benefit Risk Ratio 10:12

Save for this site only
save locally

Save for further sites
save in Consentor Cloud

Learn more at [consentor](#)

MY PLANTSHOP

SO MANY AMAZING PLANTS

Do you agree to give your consent to this site?

Customise Confirm